

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 1.15 Data Management Plan

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1. Summary

The Data Management Plan (DMP) identified and describe each data used in the project and explains how these data are compliant with the existing suitable standards. The document also defines how data could be shared and which procedures are needed for a long-term preservation of the data.

Therefore, the purpose of this Deliverable D1.15 is to provide the plan for managing the data generated and collected during the entire lifetime of the CYCLOPES project. The CYCLOPES Data Management Plan will cover both confidential and public data to be produced within the project, and due processes for the both types of data will be defined. Moreover, this Deliverable D1.15, is touching issues partly described in Deliverable D8.2 POPD - Requirement No. 2 and in Deliverable D1.14 CYCLOPES Project Security Guideline.

2. Introduction

Good research data management is not goal in itself, but rather the key conduit leading to knowledge discovery and innovation, and to subsequent data and knowledge integration and reuse. The Data Management Plans (DMPs) are a key element of good data management and describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected during the project, processed and/or generated by a research project. According to the European Commission's Directorate-General on Research and Innovation's Guidelines on Data Management¹, as part of making research data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR), a DMP should cover information on:

- the handling of research data during and after the end of the project
- what data will be collected, processed and/or generated
- which methodology and standards will be applied
- whether data will be shared/made open access and
- how data will be curated and preserved.

The European Commission requires H2020 beneficiaries to accomplish with Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP). The ORDP aims to improve and maximise access to research data generated by selected Horizon 2020 projects accessible with as few restrictions as possible, while at the same time protecting sensitive data from inappropriate access. To achieve it is mandatory to define a Data Management Plan (DMP). Being a part of the ORDP, the CYCLOPES consortium is committed to provide Open Access (free-of-charge access) to all scientific publications and associated research data.

3. CYCLOPES Data Management Plan

The Data Management Plan (DMP) sets out guidelines for the management of data during the CYCLOPES project. The purpose of the DMP is to provide an analysis of the main elements of the data management policy with regards to all the datasets that will be generated by the

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

project. The DMP should address the points presented below on a dataset by dataset basis and should reflect the current status of reflection within the consortium about the data that will be generated, collected, stored and processed.

Therefore, this section describes the Data Management strategy of the CYCLOPES project to achieve the data used in the project. The general strategy for data management, according to the Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020, will be based on:

- identification and classification of data collected and generated by the project
- definition of the methodology for data exploitation, availability of data and access, sharing, and re-use of data
- definition of a policy for data archiving and data preservation
- ethical and legal compliance

3.1. Data collection and generation

During the CYCLOPES project lifetime, the following categories of qualitative and quantitative data will be collected, extracted and generated as a result of data processing. That can be summarized as:

- data related to LEA requirements in area of technology, legal, organisational, trainings
- data related to the use of technology by LEAs in various domains
- data related to CYCLOPES Practitioners Workshops
- data related to new technology advances in support of LEAs
- data related to LEAs procurement programs
- data related to standards for technologies and solutions used by LEAs

Any collected personal data will be promptly deleted five years after the end of the project lifetime. The data collected in the project will not be used further for any purpose incompatible with the original purpose of collection. All the rights of the data subjects, e.g. right to object, right of access, and right to rectify, erase or block will be ensured².

3.2. Data sources

The CYCLOPES project involves primary data collection from different sources: 1) Survey questionnaires; 2) Practitioners' workshops, 3) Research, innovation and market watch, 4) Joint Live Exercises, 5) Annual standardisation workshops.

- 1) Survey Questionnaires:** questionnaires prepared by WP2 and WP3 and given to participants of the CYCLOPES practitioners' workshops organised within WP2.
- 2) Practitioners' workshops:** information collected from practitioners during CYCLOPES practitioners' workshops organised within WP2.
- 3) Research, innovation and market watch:** information collected by WP3 activities described in deliverable D3.1.

² Details of how personal data will be collected and managed are described in CYCLOPES deliverables D7.1 and D8.1

- 4) **Joint Live Exercises:** information collected during testing the selected products and solutions identified by the innovation market and research watch, within WP3.
- 5) **Annual standardisation workshops:** information collected through the CYCLOPES annual workshops and related work conducted, within WP4.

3.3. Types of data

Data collected or produced by the CYCLOPES project can be either:

- Personal data: data which relate to an individual who can be identified.
- Non-personal data: data not affected by national or European Data Protection legislation.

As the project will not focus on personal data for law enforcement purposes (e.g. data about offenders) but solely process the personal data of members of the law enforcement community (and people outside the law enforcement community) – for example for the purpose of interviews, the frameworks specific to the work of law enforcement will not apply. The project involves predominantly law enforcement participants but will also involve participants outside the law enforcement community. As a consequence, different data protection legal frameworks need to be taken into consideration when examining the legal framework:

- The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) applies as of 25 May 2018 and is part of the new data protection reform package together with the Data Protection Directive for the police and criminal justice sector (Police Directive -Directive (EU) 2016/680);
- The Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data of the Council of Europe and its Recommendation No R(87) 154.

3.4. Metadata standards

Metadata is information that makes your new data usable. Most of the means used to collect data in the respective datasets are based on structured questionnaires and/or Workshop results.

The metadata for the different identified datasets will be generated through manual content annotation. The means with which metadata will be generated, if at all, is described in each of the respective dataset entries in Annex 1.

3.5. Exploitation, availability of data and re-use

The Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement of CYCLOPES project (particularly Section 3 Rights and Obligations Related to Background and Results) are to be referred to for further details on the ownership of results, management of intellectual property and access rights.

3.6. Data storage and backup

Any personal data and technical comment that will be collected in the CYCLOPES project lifetime will be stored electronically in the CYCLOPES repository on TEAMS so that all the consortium partners will have access to them. Every partner is responsible to ensure that the data are stored safely and securely. These data will not be shared and cannot be accessed and copied by any external party.

Any relevant data marked as RESTREINT EU/EU RESTRICTED, will be stored in a locked container, according to the rules and procedures described in deliverable D1.14 “Cyclopes Project Security Guideline”.

Any collected personal data will be deleted from the project’s data storage five years after the end of the project. Upon the request of stakeholders, their personal data will be deleted from the project repositories.

3.7. Preservation of the datasets

It has yet to be decided by the CYCLOPES Consortium which project datasets will be preserved, the duration of this preservation period, and the costs that such preservation will entail. More details regarding data preservation will be available as the project develops and will be duly reported in subsequent versions of the present deliverable.

3.8. Ethical and legal compliance

The CYCLOPES project ensures that data will be processed in line with all applicable legislation and regulations.

3.9. Responsibility and resources

The responsibility for adhering to the guidelines set out by this Data Management Plan lies in particular with the Project Coordinator (PC) but also with Work Packages Leaders (WPL) and the individual partners in the CYCLOPES Consortium.

To make sure the guidelines in this document are clear and sufficient, and that they are followed, the CYCLOPES Data Protector Officer will be in frequent consultation with the Project Coordinator, Project Management Office and Work Packages Leaders. The CYCLOPES DPO provides expert advice on data protection and educates staff on data protection compliance requirements. CYCLOPES DPO answers questions and inquiries of data subjects and is a point of contact for data protection supervisory authority.

4. CYCLOPES datasets

In order to minimise the risk of malevolent use of data, the data has to be handled restrictively. Therefore, the following aspects related to the CYCLOPES datasets are described in below table. It presents the current status of reflection within the consortium in relation to the set of data that will be produced by the project.

Table 1 Aspects related to the CYCLOPES datasets

Dataset name and reference	A unique name (project identifier) for the dataset to be used as a reference to this dataset in the CYCLOPES project.
Dataset description	A brief description of the dataset as a whole and variables in the dataset.
Standards and metadata	A reference to existing suitable standards of the discipline. If these do not exist, an outline on how and what metadata will be created will be given instead.
Data sharing	A detailed description of how data will be shared, including access procedures, outlines of technical mechanisms for dissemination and necessary software and other tools for enabling re-use, and definition of whether access will be widely open or restricted to specific groups. Identification of the repository where data will be stored, if already existing and identified, indicating in particular the type of repository.

	In case the dataset cannot be shared, the reasons for this should be mentioned (e.g. ethical, rules of personal data, intellectual property, and commercial, privacy-related, security related).
Archiving and preservation	A description of the procedures that will be put in place for long term preservation of the data. Indication of how long the data should be preserved, what is its approximated end volume, what the associated costs are and how these are planned to be covered.

The template for the description of the CYCLOPES datasets using the structure recommended by the European Commission’s Directorate-General on Research and Innovation’s Guidelines on Data Management you can find in Annex 1.

5. Conclusion

This Data Management Plan (DMP) provides a broad analysis of the data that will be generated, processed and/or stored by CYCLOPES project. It provides a description of the methods to be used in terms of making CYCLOPES data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. The document also provides an explanation about the allocation of resources which assures CYCLOPES generated data would be preserve and accessible after the end of the project.

A final version of this plan will be reported in M60 under Deliverable D1.16 The Final Data Management Plan.

List of Tables

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Annex 1 CYCLOPES Dataset template

1. Dataset name and reference	<p>DATASET 1: Dataset Name Dataset Reference: Link will be provided at later stage of CYCLOPES project.</p>
2. Dataset description	<p>This dataset consists of the answers of printed questionnaires/ Workshop results with the aim of producing a set of LEA requirements/associated technology in specific areas as part of WPX and related Practitioner Group Workshop. It will be in the form of .txt files and excel spreadsheets.</p>
3. Standards and metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • quantitative and qualitative survey data from filled in questionnaires • text files in .txt format or excel spreadsheets in .xls format. • Dataset will employ Snowball Sampling (Non-probability sampling technique among Partners – Associates). <p>Files will be structured as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • name of the project; • file name; • revision number (if any); • date in the format of month and year.
4. Data sharing	<p>This data is non-restricted information and will be shared or licensed for reuse.</p>
5. Archiving and preservation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data will be stored on institutional servers • Full back-up of data occurs automatically according to a predefined schedule